

Supporting Information:

Guanidinium Like-Charge Ion Pairing and Oligoarginine Aggregation in Water by NMR, Cryo-Electron Microscopy, and Molecular Dynamics

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NMR Experiments

Figure S1: ^1H -NMR and ^{13}C -NMR shifts of GdmCl solution in neat water.

Figure S2: ^1H -NMR and ^{13}C -NMR shifts as a function of Gdm^+ concentration in an aqueous solution, where a constant ionic strength of ~ 6 M is maintained by adding NaCl.

Figure S3: The concentration dependence of ^1H NMR signal of guanidinium chloride (left) and ammonium chloride (right) in an aqueous solution, where a constant ionic strength of 3 M is maintained by adding NaCl.

Electronic Structure Calculations

Figure S4: Optimized Gdm⁺-Gdm⁺ (top) and NH₄⁺-NH₄⁺ (bottom) dimers at B3LYP-D3-aug-cc-pVDZ level of theory. Gdm⁺ and NH₄⁺ ions are depicted in blue and red colors, respectively, using QuickSurf visualization in VMD,^{S1} with these colors corresponding to the data lines in other figures for consistency.

Figure S5: The dependence of the ^{13}C -NMR chemical shift for the $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ dimer on the distance between guanidinium carbons. The data are calculated from quantum chemical calculations at the PCM/B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ//B3LYP-D3-aug-cc-pVDZ level of theory. All NMR shifts are referenced to tetramethylsilane.

Table S1: Calculated ^{13}C -NMR chemical shifts for the $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ dimer and Gdm^+ monomer, along with the corresponding differences, calculated using quantum mechanical methods with different levels of theory. * Calculated NMR shifts were corrected using the approach from Hoyt et al, relative to aldehyde as a reference.

Method	Monomer [ppm]	Dimer [ppm]	Δ [ppm]
B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ//B3LYP-D3-cc-pVDZ	160.19	158.78	1.41
B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ//B3LYP-D3-aug-cc-pVDZ	160.17	159.40	0.77
B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,p)//B3LYP-D3-6-31+G(d)	160.47	159.62	0.85
B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ//B3LYP-D3-aug-cc-pVDZ*	221.11	220.31	0.80

Molecular Dynamics Simulations

Figure S6: Radial distribution functions $g_{\text{Cz}^-\text{Cl}^-}(r)$ from MD simulations of GdmCl/NaCl solutions at a constant ionic strength of ~ 3 M. The data are presented only for the prosECCo75 force field, and the profiles are essentially identical. The same conclusions can be made from the profiles collected using the other tested force fields (KB and KB2, data not shown).

Figure S7: Radial distribution functions $g_{C_z-C_z}(r)$ and $g_{N_z-N_z}(r)$ from MD simulations of ~ 3 M GdmCl and NH₄Cl solutions, *i.e.*, in the absence of NaCl.

Figure S8: Potential of mean force calculated from the radial distribution functions from MD simulations of ~ 3 M GdmCl solutions, *i.e.*, in the absence of NaCl.

Table S2: Estimation of $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ binding free energy ΔG_b from MD simulations using different force fields and varying the total ionic strength and Gdm^+ concentration.

Force Field	Total / Gdm^+ Concentration [M]	ΔG_b [$\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$]
prosECCo75	3 / 0.1	-2.5
	3 / 3	-1.1
	6 / 0.5	-3.1
	6 / 6	-0.6
KB2	3 / 0.1	-1.4
	3 / 3	-0.6
	6 / 0.5	-1.7
	6 / 6	-0.4

Figure S9: The ion pairing of the NH_4^+ cations as a function of NH_4^+ concentration in an aqueous solution, where a constant ionic concentration of ~ 3 M is maintained by adding NaCl. The degree of like-charge pairing is denoted by diamonds and circles for 4.5 Å and 4.7 Å N_z-N_z cutoff distances, respectively. The thick dashed line connects the data points and is just a guide for the eye. The thin line links the origin to the maximum concentration, indicating potential nonlinearity in the data. The standard deviation calculated by dividing the analysis into five equal time intervals does not exceed 0.3% (smaller than the data symbols) and is therefore not shown.

Figure S10: The ion pairing of the Gdm^+ cations as a function of Gdm^+ concentration in an aqueous solution, where a constant ionic concentration of either ~ 3 M or ~ 6 M is maintained by adding NaCl. The degree of like-charge pairing is denoted by diamonds and circles for 3.9 Å and 4.5 Å C_z-C_z cutoff distances, respectively. The thick dashed line connects the data points and is just a guide for the eye. The thin line links the origin to the maximum concentration, indicating potential nonlinearity in the data. The standard deviation calculated by dividing the analysis into five equal time intervals does not exceed 0.6% (smaller than the data symbols) and is therefore not shown.

Figure S11: Comparison of the spatial distribution of ions and solvent around the central guanidinium (Gdm^+) cation (in van der Waals representation) in aqueous (top row), methanol (middle row), and ethanol (bottom row) 0.5 M GdmCl solutions. The left column presents the distribution of ions: Gdm^+ (cyan, representing the C-atom) and chloride (Cl^-) (orange). The middle column presents the distribution of solvent: oxygen atoms of water or alcohol hydroxyl oxygen atoms (red), and carbons of methyl groups of alcohols (black). The right column presents an illustration of the intrinsic arrangement. The isocontour levels (referenced to the average bulk density, ρ_0) are: in ethanol, Gdm^+ (C_z) at $30 \times \rho_0$, Cl^- at $80 \times \rho_0$, EtOH (OOH) at $4 \times \rho_0$, and CCH_3 at $40 \times \rho_0$; in methanol, Gdm^+ (C_z) at $20 \times \rho_0$, Cl^- at $40 \times \rho_0$, MeOH (OOH) at $4 \times \rho_0$, and CCH_3 at $40 \times \rho_0$; in water, Gdm^+ (C_z) at $3 \times \rho_0$, Cl^- at $20 \times \rho_0$, and water (OW) at $4 \times \rho_0$.

Figure S12: Radial distribution function between Gdm^+ cations (represented by C_z atoms) as obtained from MD simulation of 0.5 M GdmCl in water, methanol, and ethanol solutions. Due to significant cation–anion association, the C_z – C_z RDFs in alcohols are, in the left panel, scaled down (by their maxima) to allow direct comparison of preference between contact Gdm^+ – Gdm^+ stacking and more separated configurations. The right panel presents raw RDFs.

CryoEM Experiments

Figure S13: (A) Comparison of radial profiles derived from FFT power spectra images of 100 mM R₉ (blue) and buffer-only samples (gray). (B) Comparison of radial profiles derived from FFT power spectra images of 100 mM K₉ (red) and buffer-only samples (gray). (C) Comparison of spatial ACFs measured from cryo-EM images of 100 mM R₉ (blue) and buffer-only solutions (gray). (D) Comparison of spatial ACFs measured from cryo-EM images of 100 mM K₉ (red) and buffer-only solutions (gray). Data are presented as median \pm median absolute deviation (MAD), based on $n = 205$ frames for R₉, $n = 152$ frames for K₉, and $n = 141$ frames for buffer-only samples.

References

- (S1) Humphrey, W.; Dalke, A.; Schulten, K. VMD: Visual molecular dynamics. *J. Mol. Graph.* **1996**, *14*, 33–38.